

Social Dominance Orientation, Self-esteem, and Intergroup Preferences in University Students

Shraddhesh Kumar Tiwari

Post Doctoral Fellow, Department of Psychology, Deen Dayal Upadhyay Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur

Arati Pandey

Associate Professor, B.R.D.B.D.P.G. College, Ashram Barhaj, Deoria

Dhananjay Kumar

Professor, Department of Psychology, Deen Dayal Upadhyay Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur

Abstract

This study investigates the association among social dominance orientation, self-esteem, and intergroup preferences in three social categories university students. 360 male and female students were included from three social categories general, OBC and SC/ST category. Social dominance orientation (SDO) scale, explicit self-esteem scale (ESE), Single Item Measure of Implicit Self Esteem (ISE) and Intergroup preference scale were used. SDO dimension hierarchy enhancement was found positively correlated with intergroup preference in all three social categories whereas, implicit self-esteem surname positively correlated for OBC and negatively correlated for general category in SC/ST category participants. Study highlights the need for group evaluation, identification versus disidentification psychological mechanism and its impact on current researches i.e., cross cultural, race, ethnicity, and application to group remedy and intervention.

Keywords: Social dominance Orientation, Explicit self-esteem, Implicit self-esteem, Group Preferences.

Introduction

The social structure of any society and people's identity is greatly influenced by gender, class, religion, place of birth, local language, etc. In the Indian scenario, the distinctive feature is diversity i.e., caste, category, surname, which adheres to earlier Indians in ancient history, fostering the division of social groups, social class and ranking people high or low in terms of their wealth, power and privilege. SDO theory proposes a group-based social hierarchy and posits that segments of social organization from prejudice to culturally legitimizing ideologies create and maintain social structures (Sidanius and Pratto 2012). Focusing on social dominance theory, Pratto et al. (2013) that almost all societies are known as social group hierarchies, in which one social group often possesses ethnic, religious, national, or racial and disproportionate power and enjoys special privileges and at least one other group has relatively little power or ease in its way of life. Dryburgh (2014) argued that because of differential group status within a hierarchy, individuals in subordinate groups may have less access to resources and opportunities, and may even have limited access or no access to certain rights. SDO theory justifies the superiority of one group over others and leads to minimal social group conflict and creates consensus and ideologies. People prefer either equal or hierarchical relationships between groups (Pratto et al. 1994), with basic individual orientation to accept and justify different forms of social inequality (Sidanius 1993).

The basic tendency of the SDO is that individual's desire to have own primary group be considered better than, superior to and dominant over relevant out group (Sidanius 1993) and affects out group discrimination, including negative stereotyping of out-group. Much research suggests that members of high-status groups want to continue to support social inequality, for example, members of high-status groups generally show greater bias to out group (Sidanius, Pratto, Martin, and Stallworth, 1991) and favoritism within the group as low-status group members even when status is randomly assigned (Bettencourt, Dorr, Charlton, & Hume, 2001).

The subjective assessment of a person's overall worthiness is termed self-esteem (Robins, Tracy, and Trzesniewski 2008) and plays a key role in social relationships (Leary 2012). Self-esteem is measured on two dimensions of positive and negative items. The result of

these two bipolar dimensions evaluates a high and a low self-esteem. High self-esteem means thinking well of yourself. This can include a sense of self-confidence and an appropriate perception of one's own performance and abilities. It can also exaggerate or far deviate from the truth. Having high self-esteem can mean being pompous, selfish, arrogant, and narcissistic.

Greenwald and Banaji (1995) define implicit self-esteem (ISE) as the imprecisely identified effect of self-attitude on evaluations of self-associated and self-dissociated objects. It is recognized as an automatic or unconscious process and plays a large role in almost all social psychological processes (Bargh et al 2001). Self-esteem was once thought to be the result of a conscious self-evaluation process, but much recent work has emphasized the role of the unconscious or implicit self-evaluation process. Researchers distinguish between ISE and ESE. Explicit self-esteem is based on a conscious process, while ISE is the result of an automatic self-evaluation process. It reflects the unconscious process of association with the self (Greenwald and Banaji 1995). The tendency to favor members of one's own group over those in other groups is referred to as ingroup preference (Everett et al. 2015), while outgroup preference refers to rejection of their own category or groups. Outgroup preference arises when members of low-status groups internalize unfavorable stereotypes for themselves and favorable stereotypes for others in order to rationalize the established hierarchy (Jost and Banaji 1994).

A vast majority of research on social dominance orientation and self-esteem suggest that members belong to low advantage social group, minority groups or underprivilege people treated as subordinate group and oppressed by superior groups and manifestation of low self-esteem, outgroup favoritism and social discrimination. Appropriate research database is available in western countries but in Indian scenario, researches gap on social dominance orientation, social identity based ingroup and out group preferences and level of ESE and ISE are seen. Therefore, the main aim of the study was to determine the association between social dominance orientation, self-esteem (explicit and implicit), and intergroup preference in university students. With this view in mind, the specific objectives of the study were to 1) examine the relationship between social dominance orientation and intergroup preference in three social categories of students, 2) examine the relationship between self-esteem (explicit and implicit) and intergroup preferences in three social categories of students, 3) to compare the level of social dominance orientation, self-esteem (explicit and implicit), and intergroup preferences of three social categories of students.

Method

Sample: The sample consisted of 360 college students (equal number of each social category, gender, and income level) from the university and its affiliated colleges in the same city. They were students of various graduate and postgraduate courses (whether arts, business, humanities, or science). The age range of the participants was between 15 and 32 years. The average age was determined to be 20.79 years.

Measures

Social Dominance Orientation Scale (SDO Scale): This scale was developed by Pratto et al (2013). Hindi translation was carried out by Shraddhesh Kumar Tiwari and Dhananjay Kumar. This scale contains four items in which two items promote greater degree of social inequality, and another two items promote greater social equality. All items were answered on seven-point scale with 1 (strongly agree/disapproval) and 7 (strongly agree/approval).

Coopersmith Explicit Self-Esteem (1982): The inventory consists 25 items in English language. Hindi adaption of this scale was completed by Shraddhesh Kumar Tiwari and Dhananjay Kumar (2014) with 24 items. Reliability coefficient of English language scale was ranging from .71 to .80 in different researches.

Single Item Measure of Implicit Self Esteem (Gebauer, Riketta, Broemer, and Maio's 2008): In this approach, three questions are presented and asked them "How much they like their name, surname and total" separately on seven-point scale.

Intergroup Preference Scale: It contains five items and assess the group preferences among social categories. This scale presents five situation and ask about each situation three time, one for self-category and two times other social categories. The main theme of the questions was to assess the preference in condition of making friends, whenever do any important tasks, study for examination or competitive exams, personal feelings sharing and overall evaluation of happiness, health and wellbeing. All items were administered three times and responses were taken on four-point scale strongly agree (4) to strongly disagree (1). Cronbach’s alpha for three social categories was remained acceptable and spread from 0.78 for general category, 0.69 for other backward category and 0.78 for scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category.

Results

Social Dominance Orientation and Intergroup Preference: To understand the relationship among the dimensions of social dominance orientation and intergroup preference for three social categories, Pearson Product moment Correlation was performed. The findings of correlations have been presented category wise.

Table 1: Correlations among dimensions of social dominance orientations and intergroup preferences in three social categories

Respondent social category	Behavioral orientations	Dimensions of SDO Hierarchy	
	Preference about respected social category	Enhancement	Attenuation
General Category	General category	.275**	-.173
	Other backward category	.030	.025
	SC/ST category	-.062	-.051
Other Backward Category	General category	.158	-.067
	Other backward category	.271*	-.106
	SC/ST category	.142	-.129
SC/ST Category	General category	-.028	-.153
	Other backward category	-.008	.107
	SC/ST category	.289**	.059

Note: **p<.01, *p<.05

It is evident from the table 1 that hierarchy enhancement was found positively relationship with general category preference ($r=.275, p<.01$) in general category, other backward category preference ($r=.271, p<.05$) in other backward category and preference to scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category ($r=.289, p<.01$) in SC/ST category. Thus, it can say that this trend demonstrates the ingroup favoritism in in all three social categories.

Table 2: Correlations among Implicit and explicit self-esteem and intergroup preferences in three social categories

Respondent social category	Behavioral orientations Preference about respected social category	Explicit self esteem	Self Esteem (Explicit and Implicit)		
			Implicit self esteem		
			Name	Surname	Name and Surname
General Category	General category	-.009	.024	.167	.103
	Other backward category	-.034	-.096	.106	-.006
	SC/ST category	-.062	-.184	.058	.035
Other Backward Category	General category	.011	.066	.158	.117
	Other backward category	-.018	.127	.209*	.124
	SC/ST category	-.096	.115	.033	.010
SC/ST Category	General category	-.027	.070	-.182*	-.097
	Other backward category	.074	.066	-.068	-.120
	SC/ST category	.076	.025	-.041	.051

Note: **p<.01, *p<.05

Table 2 illustrates the relationship among explicit self-esteem and dimensions of implicit self-esteem. There are not significant relationship found in general category members, whereas a significant positive association between other backward category preference and implicit self-esteem surname ($r=.209, p<.05$) in other backward category. However, in SC/ST category, a significant negative relationship was found ($r=-.182, p<.05$) between preference to general category and implicit self-esteem surname in SC/ST category.

Effect of social category on social dominance orientation, self-esteem (explicit and implicit) and intergroup preference

Table-3: Mean, SD and F value of hierarchy enhancement and hierarchy attenuation as a function of three social categories

Dimensions	Social Categories	Mean	SD	F
Social Dominance Orientation				
Hierarchy Enhancement	General	6.48	3.44	1.14
	OBC	6.58	3.26	
	SC/ST	7.04	3.13	
Hierarchy Attenuation	General	11.83	2.37	1.505
	OBC	11.92	2.19	
	SC/ST	12.28	1.90	
Self esteem				
Explicit Self esteem	General	56.40	12.89	1.63
	OBC	54.88	13.38	
	SC/ST	53.47	11.28	
Implicit self-esteem (Name)	General	6.40	1.12	.129
	OBC	6.33	1.00	
	SC/ST	6.36	1.09	
Implicit self-esteem (Surname)	General	6.41	1.20	13.94**
	OBC	6.07	1.30	
	SC/ST	5.43	1.81	
Implicit self -esteem (Name and Surname)	General	6.43	1.17	7.28**
	OBC	6.18	1.05	
	SC/ST	5.83	1.45	
Intergroup Preference				
Preference to General category	General	11.74	3.65	1.10
	OBC	11.33	2.80	
	SC/ST	11.89	2.60	
Preference to OBC	General	10.91	2.47	3.33*
	OBC	11.52	3.12	
	SC/ST	11.80	2.59	
Preference to SC/ST category	General	10.39	3.00	25.85**
	OBC	10.67	2.35	
	SC/ST	12.83	3.18	

Note: ** $p<.01$, * $p<.05$

Implicit self-esteem surname was found significant [$F(1,358) = 13.94, p<.01$] on the level of three social categories. Respective mean scores suggest that general category participants have got highest score on implicit self-esteem surname in comparison to other backward category and scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category members. Implicit self-esteem (Name and Surname) has been found significant [$F(1,358) = 7.28, p<.01$]. General category members manifested higher implicit self-esteem in comparison to other backward category and scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category members. Moreover, the social categories effect was found significant [$F(1,358) = 3.33, p<.05$] on preference to OBC category. SC/ST category participants were mostly preferred to OBC category participants. Significant impact of social category was found on preference to SC/ST category [$F(1,358) = 25.85, p<.01$]. SC/ST category members were given maximum preference to self-category. General category members have been given least preference to SC/ST category in comparison to OBC category.

Discussion

The associated hypothesis states that a significant relationship would be found between the dimensions of social dominance orientations and intergroup preference. In general category university students, a significant positive relationship ($p < .01$) was found between general category preference and social dominance orientation hierarchy enhancement. In other backward category, social dominance orientation hierarchy enhancement and other backward category preference was found positive relationship. ($p < .05$). In SC/ST category, SDO hierarchy enhancement and SC/ST preference was found significant relationship ($p < .01$). In all three social categories SDO enhancement and self-category preference suggest the in-group favoritism.

Correlation coefficient between self-esteem and intergroup preference suggest the significant positive relationship ($p < .05$) between other backward category preference and implicit self-esteem surname in general category members, however, pattern of ingroup favoritism was seen in OBC category data whereas, a negative relationship between general category preference and implicit self-esteem Surname reveals the picture of out group favoritism. It means surname of SC/ST category members affects the implicit self-esteem. Findings of the study remained the in-group favoritism in OBC category and SC/ST category members. Possible reason behind ingroup favoritism in three social categories could be that all participants were from urban residence. It could be seen that urbanization and awareness about reservation policy and group reunion occurs in urban specially district headquarters and a university and colleges are seen as a meeting hub and aware with caste category meeting and students' rights in educational institutes.

ISE surname in three social categories found significant difference ($p < .01$) in university students. Implicit self-esteem surname is a very important construct of social psychology. However, social dominance orientation hierarchy enhancement and hierarchy attenuation dimension were not found significant it means three social categories members reflects common evaluation but, still surname that is prove the social identity reduce the implicit self-esteem for social cate/category. Definition of implicit self-esteem is given by Greenwald and Banaji (1995) as inaccurately identified effect of self-attitude on evaluation of self-associated and self-disassociated objects. It is recognized as automatic or unconscious process and play a major role in almost all social psychological process (Bargh and Chartrand 1999, Bargh 2001). Explicit self-esteem is based on conscious process whereas implicit self-esteem is the result of automatic self-evaluation process. It reflects unconscious process association with the self (Greenwald and Banaji 1995). There was not found significant effect of social category on explicit self-esteem. People with high implicit self-esteem display positivity towards themselves and object associated with themselves (letters in their name), whereas, people with low implicit self-esteem exhibit relatively less positivity for them and associated objects (Bosson, Swann and Pennebaker 2000).

Preference towards other backward category was found significant ($p < .05$) and scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category university students gave more score in comparison to general category. Preference to scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category was found significant ($p < .01$) and scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category members labeled high score for self-group preference. Tajfel and Turner (1986), Turner (1975) explained the reason for ingroup and outgroup preference. People tend to view themselves positively, and because group membership is an important part of self-concept, people tend to view their own groups more positively than other groups. According to social identity theory, there is a general drive to improve individual and collective self-esteem by making favorable comparisons between ingroups and relevant outgroups (Hogg and Abrams, 1988).

Conclusions

Study emphasizes the social dominance orientation's dimensions, self-esteem and intergroup preferences especially in intergroup relational context. Response's pattern of three social categories on self-group and other two social groups reveal the intergroup thoughts and

attitude of category members which is established by government of India. Correlational results of social dominance orientation and intergroup preference indicate the ingroup favoritism whereas, in other backward category followed same pattern with implicit self-esteem and scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category members manifested out group favoritism for general category members. The negative relationship between general category preference and scheduled caste/scheduled tribe implicit self-esteem surname asserts direct impact on social categorization system of Indian government. Significant difference on implicit self-esteem surname, intergroup preference for other backward category and scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category proves the social group evaluation of the participants.

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References:

- Bargh, J.A., Gollwitzer, P.M., Lee-Chai, A., Bamdollar, K., & Trötschel, R. (2001). The automated will: Nonconscious activation and pursuit of behavioural goals. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 81(6), 1014–1027.
- Bargh, J.A. & Chartrand, T.L. (1999). The unbearable automaticity of being. *American Psychologist*, 54, 462-479.
- Bettencourt, B. A., Dorr, N., Charlton, K., & Hume, D.L. (2001). Status differences and ingroup bias: A meta-analytic examination of the effects of status stability, status legitimacy, and group permeability. *Psychological Bulletin*, 127, 520-542.
- Bosson, J.K., Swann, W.B. Jr., Pennebaker, J.W. (2000) Stalking the perfect measure of implicit self-esteem: the blind men and the elephant revisited? *J Pers Soc Psychol*. 79(4):631-43.
- Cooper Smith, S. (1982). *The antecedents of self-esteem*. Palo Alto, CA: consulting Psychologist press
- Dryburgh, N.S.J. (2014). *The Relation of Social Dominance Orientation to Moral Decision-Making Using a Process Dissociation Approach*. Undergraduate Honors Theses.
- Everett, J.A.C., Faber, N.S., & Crockett, M. (2015). Preferences and beliefs in ingroup favouritism. *Frontiers in Behavioural Neuroscience*, 9, Article 15.
- Gebauer, J.E., Riketta, M., Broemer, P., & Maio, G.R. (2008). How much do you like your name? An implicit measure of global self-esteem. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 44, 1346-1354.
- Greenwald, A.G., & Banaji, M.R. (1995). Implicit social cognition: Attitude, Self-esteem and Stereotypes. *Psychological Review*, 102, 4-27.
- Hogg, M.A. & Abrams, D. (1988). *Social identification. A social psychology of intergroup relations and group processes*. London: Routledge.
- Jost, J.T. and Banaji. M.R. (1994). The role of stereotyping in system justification and the production of false consciousness. *British journal of social psychology*, 33, 1-27.
- Leary, M.R. (2012). Sociometer theory. In P.A.M. Van Lange, A.W. Kruglanski, & E.T. Higgins (Eds.), *Handbook of theories of social psychology* (pp. 151–159). Sage Publications Ltd.
- Pratto, F., Sidanius, J., Stallworth, L.M., & Malle, B.F. (1994). Social dominance orientation: A personality variable predicting social and political attitudes. *Journal of Personality & Social Psychology*, 67, 741-763.
- Pratto, F., Çidam, A., Stewart, A.L., et al (2013) Social Dominance in Context and in Individuals: Contextual Moderation of Robust Effects of Social Dominance Orientation in 15 Languages and 20 Countries *Social Psychological and Personality Science* 4(5) 587-599.
- Robins, R.W., Tracy, J.L., & Trzesniewski, K. H. (2008). Naturalizing the Self. In O.P. John, R. W. Robins, & L.A. Pervin (Eds.), *Handbook of personality: Theory and research* (3rd ed., pp. 421– 447). New York, NY: Guilford Press.
- Sidanius, J. (1993). The psychology of group conflict and the dynamics of oppression: A social dominance perspective. In W. McGuire & S. Iyengar (Eds.), *Current approaches to political psychology* (pp. 183-219). Durham, NC: Duke University Press
- Sidanius, J., & Pratto, F. (2012). Social dominance theory. In P.A.M. Van Lange, A.W. Kruglanski, & E. T. Higgins (Eds.), *Handbook of theories of social psychology* (pp. 418–438). Sage Publications Ltd.
- Sidanius, J., Pratto, F., Martin, M., & Stallworth, L. (1991b). Consensual racism and career track: Some implications of social dominance theory. *Political Psychology*, 12, 691 – 721.
- Tajfel, H., & Turner, J.C. (1986). The social identity theory of intergroup behavior. In S. Worehel & W.G. Turner, J.C. (1975). Social comparison and social identity: Some prospects for intergroup behaviour. *European Journal of social psychology*, 5, 5-34.

